

The Relationship Between Spirituality and Work Attitude Among Nurses Employed at Novaliches District Hospital

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Abstract. Spirituality is increasingly recognized as a factor that may influence how nurses respond to workplace demands and patient care responsibilities. In hospital settings, spiritual well-being may help strengthen meaning, resilience, compassion, and commitment to service, which are important in sustaining positive professional behavior. This study examined the relationship between spirituality and work attitude among nurses employed at Novaliches District Hospital. Specifically, it described the respondents' demographic profile, determined their level of spiritual well-being, assessed their work attitude, and tested the relationship between the two variables. A descriptive-correlational research design was utilized. Thirty registered nurses, including Nurse I, Nurse II, and Contract of Service nurses, participated in the study. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire composed of three parts: demographic profile, a 10-item adapted Spiritual Well-Being Scale, and a 20-item work attitude questionnaire adapted from the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire. The data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. Frequency counts and percentages were used to describe demographic characteristics, while mean and standard deviation were computed for spiritual well-being and work attitude. Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient was used to examine the relationship between the variables. The findings showed that the respondents had a moderately high level of spiritual well-being and a generally positive work attitude. Correlation analysis revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between spirituality and work attitude, $r = 0.454$, $p = 0.012$. These findings suggest that nurses with higher spiritual well-being tend to demonstrate more favorable professional attitudes. Spirituality may therefore support resilience, compassion, and sustained commitment in nursing practice.

Keywords: Nurses; Spiritual Well-Being; Spirituality; Work Attitude; Workplace Well-Being

Introduction

Nursing is widely recognized as one of the most demanding professions in healthcare, requiring not only technical competence but also emotional resilience, sound judgment, and sustained commitment to patient care. Nurses frequently work long shifts under conditions of high workload and limited resources, which can significantly influence their job satisfaction, motivation, and retention. Recent evidence indicates that prolonged stress and heavy workloads increase the risk of burnout and are associated with poorer patient outcomes and higher staff turnover (Pappa et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2020).

In response to these challenges, spirituality has gained attention as a potential coping resource. Defined as a sense of meaning, purpose, or connection to a higher reality, spirituality may help nurses manage emotional strain and maintain professional engagement. Studies conducted during and after the COVID-19 pandemic suggest that higher levels of spiritual well-being are associated with improved resilience and emotional coping among nurses (Rogers et al., 2022; Woo et al., 2025).

In the Philippine context, where spirituality is deeply embedded in cultural and professional life, nurses often view spiritual practices as integral to holistic care and personal well-being (Bangcola, 2021; Garcia & Martinez, 2024). However, existing literature remains limited, particularly in public hospital settings where resource constraints are more pronounced. Moreover, few studies have examined how spirituality relates to measurable work attitudes, such as job satisfaction, motivation, and professional commitment, especially in post-pandemic healthcare conditions.

Addressing this gap, the present study aimed to examine the relationship between spirituality and work attitude among nurses employed at Novaliches District Hospital. Specifically, it sought to determine the nurses' level of spiritual well-being, assess their work attitude, and identify whether a significant relationship exists between these two variables. By generating locally relevant evidence, the study seeks to contribute to workplace strategies that support resilience, reduce burnout, and promote compassionate and sustained nursing practice.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the relationship between spirituality and work attitude among nurses employed at Novaliches District Hospital.

Specifically, this study aimed to:

1. Describe the demographic profile of nurses in terms of age, sex, civil status, religion, highest educational attainment, area of assignment, and years in service.
2. Determine the level of spirituality among nurses.
3. Assess the level of work attitude of nurses.
4. Examine the significant relationship between spirituality and work attitude.

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

The study focuses on the relationship of spirituality and work attitude of registered nurses (Nurse I, Nurse II, and Nurses under Contract of Service) employed at Novaliches District Hospital, assigned in the different areas of the hospital. It excludes other healthcare professionals, such as doctors, pharmacists, midwives, medical technologists, nursing administrators, and other administrative staff.

Literature Review

Recent literature suggests that spirituality may serve as an important personal and professional resource among nurses, particularly in emotionally demanding healthcare environments. In the Philippine setting, Garcia and Martinez (2024) found that nurses demonstrated high spiritual well-being awareness in both religious and existential dimensions, although their actual practice of spiritual care remained moderate. This gap between awareness and practice suggests that spirituality may be present as an internal resource but may not always be fully expressed in clinical work because of institutional constraints, workload, and limited time. This finding is relevant to the present study because it shows that spirituality may influence professional behavior, yet its relationship with measurable work attitudes still requires further examination.

Studies conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic further support the role of spirituality in helping nurses cope with emotional strain. De Diego-Cordero et al. (2022) reported that nurses drew strength from trust in God, spiritual encouragement, and spiritual growth during periods of uncertainty. Similarly, local qualitative studies described how Filipino nurses relied on spiritual beliefs to endure chronic stress and sustain their sense of professional duty during pandemic conditions (Mahinay, 2024; Wapano, 2024). These studies provide valuable insight into spirituality as a coping mechanism, but most were qualitative in nature and focused more on lived experiences, resilience, or spiritual care than on the statistical relationship between spirituality and work attitude.

Work attitude has also been examined in relation to related constructs such as work life, resilience, and engagement. Navales et al. (2021) found that uniformed nurses in the Philippines reported favorable attitudes and practices toward COVID-19 care, which were linked with quality of nursing work life. Garma (2023) similarly reported that resilience significantly predicted work engagement among nurses assigned to COVID-designated units. These studies suggest that nurses' professional attitudes may be shaped by both internal strengths and workplace conditions. However, they did not directly examine spiritual well-being as a factor associated with work attitude among nurses in a local public hospital setting.

International studies provide additional support for this relationship. Heidari et al. (2022) found that nurses with stronger spiritual well-being reported lower anxiety, higher job satisfaction, and a clearer sense of purpose in their roles. Schlak et al. (2021) also emphasized that healthy work environments, including supportive leadership, autonomy, and teamwork, were associated with reduced burnout and better nurse outcomes. More recent studies have likewise shown that spirituality and workplace support contribute to resilience, emotional stability, moral conduct, and meaning at work (López-Tarrida et al., 2024; Moez et al., 2024; Woo et al., 2025). These findings suggest that spirituality may help strengthen positive professional attitudes, but the extent of this relationship may vary across cultural and institutional contexts.

Taken together, previous studies show that spirituality is associated with resilience, coping, wellness, and positive professional behavior. However, existing local evidence remains limited, particularly in public hospital settings where nurses face workload pressure and resource constraints. Many studies have focused on spiritual care, resilience, or general well-being, while fewer have directly examined the relationship between spiritual well-being and work attitude among practicing nurses. This gap justifies the present study, which examines the relationship between spirituality and work attitude among nurses employed at Novaliches District Hospital. By focusing on a local public hospital context, the study provides evidence that may inform workplace strategies for strengthening nurses' well-being, resilience, and professional commitment.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive–correlational research design to examine the relationship between spirituality and work attitude among nurses. The design allowed for the assessment of the levels of spiritual well-being and work attitude, as well as the determination of the association between these variables without manipulation of the study environment. The descriptive component was used to present the demographic profile of the respondents and to measure the levels of spirituality and work attitude using structured questionnaires. The correlational component examined the relationship between the variables using Pearson's product–moment correlation coefficient, enabling the identification of the strength and direction of the association. This design was considered appropriate as it facilitated the investigation of naturally occurring variables within a real hospital setting while preserving the authenticity of the respondents' experiences.

Sampling Design

Convenience sampling, a non-probability sampling method, was employed in this study. Nurses who met the inclusion criteria and were available during the data collection period were recruited until a total of 30 respondents was obtained. All eligible nurses within the accessible population were invited to participate, subject to institutional permission and duty schedules. This approach was considered appropriate due to practical constraints related to staffing patterns and accessibility within the hospital setting. Although the sample size was limited, it allowed for the collection of relevant data from practicing nurses and facilitated the examination of the relationship between spirituality and work attitude. A minimum response rate of 70% was considered acceptable to ensure adequacy of the data for statistical analysis. The findings of the study are limited to the participating respondents and may not be generalizable to the entire nursing population. However, the data provide useful insights into the relationship between spirituality and work attitude among nurses in Novaliches District Hospital.

Research Locale

The study was conducted at Novaliches District Hospital, a Level 1 hospital with a 30-bed capacity that provides basic, emergency, inpatient, and outpatient services to residents of Quezon City and nearby areas. The hospital serves a diverse patient population and operates under conditions typical of public healthcare institutions, including high patient volume and resource constraints. Nurses in this setting are routinely exposed to demanding clinical workloads and dynamic care environments, which may affect their physical, emotional, and professional well-being. These conditions make the hospital an appropriate setting for examining how spirituality relates to work attitude. Investigating this relationship within a real-world public hospital context provides relevant insights into how personal and internal resources may support nurses in maintaining motivation, resilience, and quality patient care.

Research Participants

The participants of the study were nurses employed at Novaliches District Hospital during the approved period of data collection. The total nurse population of the institution was initially identified as ninety-three (93). However, due to administrative considerations and the availability of nurses endorsed by the Nursing Service Office, only thirty (30) nurses were accessible and permitted to participate during the scheduled data gathering period. These participants included Nurse I under Contract of Service, Nurse I, and Nurse II assigned in different hospital units. The study therefore focused on the accessible participants rather than the entire nurse population of the hospital. All nurses who were officially endorsed, available during the data collection period, met the inclusion criteria, and voluntarily agreed to participate were invited to take part in the study. Participation was strictly voluntary, and only those who provided informed consent were included. The final sample consisted of thirty (30) registered nurses. Although this number was relatively small compared with the total nurse population, it reflected the participants who were practically and administratively accessible without disrupting hospital operations or interfering with duty schedules. The small sample size is acknowledged as a limitation of the study, as the findings may not fully represent the views and experiences of all nurses employed at Novaliches District Hospital. Therefore, the results should be interpreted with caution and should not be generalized beyond the participants included in the study. Nevertheless, the sample provided useful preliminary evidence on the relationship between spirituality and work attitude among nurses in a local public hospital setting. Future studies may consider including a larger sample, using probability sampling, or involving multiple hospital sites to improve representativeness and generalizability.

Research Instrument

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire composed of three parts. The first part obtained the demographic profile of the respondents, including age, sex, civil status, religion, highest educational attainment, area of assignment, and years of experience. The second part measured spirituality using a 10-item adapted version of the Spiritual Well-Being Scale, which assesses both religious and existential dimensions of well-being. The third part assessed work attitude using a 20-item questionnaire adapted from the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire, covering various aspects of job satisfaction and professional attitudes. Both instruments have demonstrated acceptable reliability in previous studies. The shortened version of the SWBS reported a Cronbach’s alpha coefficient of 0.746, indicating satisfactory internal consistency (Tavel et al., 2022). The MSQ has shown high reliability, with reported Cronbach’s alpha values of up to 0.935 in recent validation studies (Pana et al., 2025).

Data Gathering Procedure

Prior to data collection, permission to conduct the study was secured from the administration of Novaliches District Hospital. The study was also reviewed by the hospital’s Data Privacy Officer through a letter, specifically in relation to privacy, confidentiality, and proper handling of research data. After the necessary institutional permission was obtained, the researcher coordinated with the Nursing Service Office regarding the schedule and availability of eligible nurse-participants. Data gathering was conducted within the hospital premises during approved periods that did not interfere with the respondents’ duty schedules or clinical responsibilities. Eligible nurses were approached based on their availability during the scheduled data collection period. The researcher briefly explained the purpose of the study and the process of answering the questionnaire before distributing the instrument to those who agreed to participate. The structured questionnaire was personally administered and retrieved by the researcher. It consisted of sections on demographic profile, spiritual well-being, and work attitude. Respondents were given sufficient time to complete the questionnaire, which required only a short period to answer. Completed questionnaires were collected immediately after completion whenever possible to ensure proper retrieval and organization of data. After collection, the responses were checked for completeness and prepared for encoding. The data were then encoded, organized, and analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic profile and variable scores, while Pearson’s product-moment correlation coefficient was used to determine the relationship between spirituality and work attitude. Ethical safeguards related to informed consent, voluntary participation, confidentiality, anonymity, and data protection are discussed separately under the Ethical Considerations section.

Results and Discussions

Problem 1: Describe the demographic profile of nurses in terms of age, sex, civil status, religion, highest educational attainment, area of assignment, and years in service.

Table 1. Demographic characteristics of the participants (n = 30)

Variable	Category	n (%)
Age	20–29	3 (10.0)
	30–39	15 (50.0)
	40–49	9 (30.0)
	≥50	3 (10.0)
Sex	Male	9 (30.0)
	Female	21 (70.0)
Civil status	Single	15 (50.0)
	Married	13 (43.3)
	Others	2 (6.7)
Religion	Roman Catholic	22 (73.3)
	Others	8 (26.7)
Highest Educational Attainment	BSN	22 (73.3)
	Post Graduate Degree	8 (26.7)
Area of Assignment	Ward	19 (63.3)
	Others	11 (36.7)
Years of Experience	≤5 years	9 (30.0)
	>5 years	21 (70.0)

As shown in Table 1, the demographic profile of the respondents shows that most nurses were in the middle stage of their professional careers, with the largest group belonging to the 30 to 39-year-old age range, followed by those aged 40 to 49 years old. Most respondents were female, single or married, Roman Catholic, Bachelor of Science in Nursing graduates, assigned in hospital wards, and had more than ten years of professional experience. These findings suggest that the sample was largely composed of clinically experienced nurses who were actively involved in direct patient care. This profile is relevant to the present study because age, years of service, and area of assignment may influence both spirituality and work attitude. Nurses in the middle stage of their careers and those with longer clinical exposure may have developed stronger coping strategies, deeper professional identity, and a clearer sense of purpose in nursing practice. Bangcola (2021) emphasized that spirituality in nursing is closely connected with holistic care and the nurse's recognition of patients' physical, emotional, and spiritual needs. In this sense, professional maturity and repeated exposure to patient care may strengthen nurses' awareness of meaning, compassion, and service. The predominance of Roman Catholic respondents also provides cultural context for interpreting the spirituality findings. In the Philippines, spirituality is often shaped by religious belief, family values, and cultural expectations of compassionate care. Garcia and Martinez (2024) found that Filipino nurses demonstrated high spiritual well-being awareness, particularly in religious and existential dimensions, although spiritual care practices were only moderately expressed. This suggests that spirituality may be strongly present among nurses, but its expression in professional behavior may still depend on workplace demands, time constraints, and institutional support. The demographic findings provide a useful background for interpreting the respondents' spiritual well-being and work attitude. The respondents' clinical maturity, ward-based assignments, religious background, and length of service may have contributed to their capacity for resilience, compassion, and sustained commitment in nursing practice. However, these demographic results should be interpreted as contextual rather than causal, since the study primarily aimed to determine the relationship between spirituality and work attitude.

Problem 2: Determine the level of spirituality among nurses.

Table 2. Spiritual Well-Being Scale (SWB) Items 1–5: Religious Well-Being

Item	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I believe that God loves me and cares about me.	30	5.90	0.40258	Strongly Agree
2. I have a personally meaningful relationship with God.	30	5.77	0.56832	Strongly Agree
3. I don't get much personal strength and support from God.	29	1.93	1.85031	Strongly Disagree
4. I believe that God is concerned about my problems.	30	5.80	0.61026	Strongly Agree
5. My relationship with God contributes to my sense of well-being.	30	5.80	0.55086	Strongly Agree
Religious Well-Being Mean	30	5.07	0.54414	Very High Level of Religious Well-being

Table 2 shows that the respondents demonstrated a very high level of religious well-being, with a mean score of 5.07. Most indicators related to religious well-being obtained very high mean scores, particularly those reflecting the nurses' relationship with God, reliance on faith, and recognition of spirituality as a meaningful part of life. This suggests that faith remains a strong personal and professional resource among the respondents. The comparatively lower score in one item may be attributed to its reverse wording in the scale rather than to weak religious orientation.

Table 3. Spiritual Well-Being Scale (SWB) Items 6–10: Existential Well-Being

Item	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I don't know who I am, where I came from, or where I am going.	30	1.80	1.47157	Strongly Disagree
2. I feel very fulfilled and satisfied with my life.	30	5.00	1.05045	Strongly Agree
3. I feel good about my future.	30	5.17	0.83391	Strongly Agree
4. Life doesn't have much meaning.	30	1.83	1.41624	Strongly Disagree
5. I believe there is some real purpose for my life.	30	5.63	0.71840	Strongly Agree
Existential Well-Being Mean	30	3.89	0.63828	Moderate Level of Existential Well-being

As shown in Table 3, existential well-being was interpreted as moderate, with a mean score of 3.89. This indicates that although many nurses experience meaning, purpose, and fulfillment in life and work, variations remain in how strongly they perceive life direction and satisfaction. These variations may be influenced by workload, emotional strain, and the realities of public hospital practice. Viewed through Frankl's concept of meaning, nurses may be better able to endure professional challenges when they connect their work with a deeper sense of purpose. Overall, the respondents had a high level of spiritual well-being, with a mean score of 4.48, suggesting that spirituality is an important aspect of their personal and professional lives. The higher religious well-being score compared with existential well-being implies that respondents may draw more strongly from faith-based beliefs than from personal life-meaning satisfaction. This finding is consistent with Bangcola (2021), who emphasized the role of spirituality in holistic nursing care, and Garcia and Martinez (2024), who found that Filipino nurses often express spirituality through compassionate presence, prayer, and emotional reassurance. Thus, spirituality may serve as an internal resource that helps nurses remain resilient, compassionate, and committed in clinical practice.

Problem 3: Assess the level of work attitude of nurses.

Table 4. Work Attitude (WA) of the Participants

Work Attitude Item	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Being able to keep busy all the time	30	3.00	5.00	3.90	0.71197	Satisfied
2. The chance to work alone on the job	30	1.00	5.00	3.50	1.10641	Satisfied
3. The chance to do different things from time to time	30	2.00	5.00	3.93	0.73968	Satisfied
4. The chance to be "somebody" in the community	30	1.00	5.00	3.67	0.95893	Satisfied
5. The way my boss handles his/her workers	30	2.00	5.00	3.80	0.92476	Satisfied
6. The competence of my supervisor in making decisions	30	2.00	5.00	3.83	0.98553	Satisfied
7. Being able to do things that don't go against my conscience.	29	2.00	5.00	3.72	0.92182	Satisfied
8. The way my job provides for steady employment	30	1.00	5.00	3.73	1.08066	Satisfied
9. The chance to do things for other people	30	3.00	5.00	4.37	0.66868	Very Satisfied
10. The chance to tell people what to do	30	3.00	5.00	3.87	0.73030	Satisfied
11. The chance to make use of my abilities	29	3.00	5.00	4.31	0.66027	Very Satisfied
12. The way company policies are put into practice	30	2.00	5.00	3.63	0.99943	Satisfied
13. My pay and the amount of work I do	29	1.00	5.00	3.45	1.21262	Satisfied
14. The chances for advancement on this job	30	2.00	5.00	3.57	1.04000	Satisfied
15. The freedom to use my own judgment	30	3.00	5.00	3.93	0.82768	Satisfied
16. The chance to try my own methods of doing the job	30	2.00	5.00	3.83	0.87428	Satisfied
17. The working conditions	30	2.00	5.00	3.70	0.87691	Satisfied
18. The way my co-workers get along with each other	30	2.00	5.00	3.97	0.80872	Satisfied
19. The praise I get for doing a good job	30	2.00	5.00	3.80	0.96132	Satisfied
20. The feeling of accomplishment I get from the job	30	3.00	5.00	4.03	0.80872	Satisfied
Overall Work Attitude (WA_Ave)	28	2.65	4.95	3.83	0.63963	High Level of Work Attitude

As shown in Table 4, the respondents exhibited a high level of work attitude, with an overall mean score of 3.83. Most indicators were interpreted as "Satisfied," suggesting that the nurses generally had positive perceptions of their work responsibilities, professional roles, and workplace experiences. Certain indicators, particularly those related to helping others and using personal abilities, were rated as "Very Satisfied." This indicates that the respondents may derive fulfillment from patient care and from opportunities to apply their skills meaningfully in the service of others. This finding suggests that despite the demanding nature of hospital work, the respondents maintained a favorable attitude toward their profession. Their positive work attitude may be influenced by both external factors, such as workplace conditions and role expectations, and internal factors, such as personal values, sense of purpose, and coping mechanisms. In relation to Jean Watson's Theory of Human Caring, nurses who find meaning in helping others may be more likely to demonstrate compassion, commitment, and patient-centered behavior in clinical practice. The result

is consistent with studies showing that spirituality and positive inner resources may support professional satisfaction and commitment among nurses. Lee (2023) found that workplace spirituality contributes to higher job satisfaction and organizational commitment among nurses. Similarly, Öcalan et al. (2023) reported that nurses with stronger spiritual orientation experienced greater compassion satisfaction and lower burnout. These findings suggest that spirituality may help sustain favorable work attitudes by strengthening nurses' sense of meaning, compassion, and professional dedication.

Problem 4: Examine the significant relationship between spirituality and work attitude.

Table 5. Correlation Analysis Between Selected Variables, Spiritual Well-Being, and Work Attitude

Variables	Age	Highest Educational Attainment	Years of Experience	Spiritual Well-Being	Work Attitude
Age of the Participants	1	.190	.470**	.177	-.054
Sig. (2-tailed)		.314	.009	.350	.777
Highest Educational Attainment of the Participants	.190	1	.238	.048	.018
Sig. (2-tailed)	.314		.205	.803	.927
Years of Experience of the Participants	.470**	.238	1	-.140	-.378*
Sig. (2-tailed)	.009	.205		.460	.039
Spiritual Well-Being (SWB_Ave)	.177	.048	-.140	1	.454*
Sig. (2-tailed)	.350	.803	.460		.012
Work Attitude (WA_Ave)	-.054	.018	-.378*	.454*	1
Sig. (2-tailed)	.777	.927	.039	.012	

As shown in Table 5, the correlation analysis examined the relationships among selected demographic variables, spiritual well-being, and work attitude. The results showed a significant positive relationship between age and years of experience, $r = .470$, $p = .009$. This indicates that older nurses tended to have longer professional experience, which is expected in clinical practice because experience generally accumulates with age and length of service. This finding provides useful background in understanding the respondents' professional maturity and clinical exposure. A significant negative relationship was also found between years of experience and work attitude, $r = -.378$, $p = .039$. This suggests that nurses with longer years of service may report slightly lower work attitude scores. This finding may be explained by prolonged exposure to workload demands, emotional fatigue, role strain, and repeated clinical pressures. While experience can strengthen competence and confidence, it may also increase responsibility and emotional burden, particularly in public hospital settings where staffing and resources may be limited. From the perspective of the Job Demands–Resources Model, prolonged job demands may weaken work motivation and satisfaction when not balanced by adequate organizational and personal resources. Most importantly, the results revealed a significant positive relationship between spiritual well-being and work attitude, $r = .454$, $p = .012$. This indicates that nurses with higher levels of spiritual well-being were more likely to demonstrate favorable attitudes toward their work. Spirituality may therefore function as an internal resource that supports motivation, compassion, emotional stability, and commitment to patient care. This finding is meaningful because it suggests that nurses' professional attitudes are not shaped only by external workplace conditions but also by personal sources of meaning and inner strength. This result is consistent with local and international literature emphasizing the value of spirituality in nursing practice. Garcia and Martinez (2024) found that Filipino nurses often express spirituality through compassionate presence, prayer, and emotional reassurance, while Bangcola (2021) explained that spirituality strengthens nurses' sense of calling, empathy, and commitment to holistic care. Internationally, Lee (2023) reported that workplace spirituality contributes to job satisfaction and organizational commitment, while Öcalan et al. (2023) found that higher spirituality was associated with greater compassion satisfaction and lower burnout. Taken together, these findings support the view that spiritual well-being may help nurses maintain positive work attitudes despite the emotional and physical demands of clinical practice. From the Job Demands–Resources perspective, spirituality may be considered a personal resource that helps nurses cope with workplace stress and remain engaged in their professional role.

Ethical Considerations

This study was conducted with due regard for the rights, dignity, privacy, and welfare of the nurse-participants. Prior to data collection, permission to conduct the study was secured from the administration of

Novaliches District Hospital. The study was also reviewed by the hospital's Data Privacy Officer through a letter dated January 9, 2026, particularly in relation to the protection of participants' privacy, confidentiality, and proper handling of research data. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary. Nurses who were invited to participate were given the freedom to decide whether they wished to join, and no form of pressure, coercion, or undue influence was applied. They were also informed that they could decline participation or withdraw from the study at any stage without penalty or negative consequence. Before answering the questionnaire, informed consent was obtained from each participant. The researcher explained the purpose of the study, its objectives, the procedures involved, the expected time needed to complete the questionnaire, and the possible risks and benefits of participation. To protect confidentiality and anonymity, no personal identifiers such as names, employee numbers, or other directly identifying information were collected or included in the analysis and reporting of results. Responses were coded and treated with strict confidentiality. The collected data were stored securely and were accessible only to the researcher. Findings were presented in aggregated form to ensure that no individual nurse could be identified. Data handling was carried out in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, or Republic Act No. 10173, particularly in relation to the lawful, fair, and secure processing of personal and research-related information. The approval obtained for the study pertained to institutional permission and data privacy review. No formal institutional ethics committee approval number was issued for this survey-based study.

Conclusion

This study concluded that nurses at Novaliches District Hospital demonstrated a high level of spiritual well-being and a generally positive work attitude. Religious well-being was higher than existential well-being, suggesting that faith remains an important personal resource among the respondents. A significant positive relationship was found between spirituality and work attitude, indicating that nurses with higher spiritual well-being tended to report more favorable attitudes toward their work. These findings suggest that spirituality may contribute to resilience, compassion, professional commitment, and a sustained sense of meaning in nursing practice. The study provides local evidence on the role of spirituality in supporting nurses' work attitudes within a public hospital setting. Future studies may use larger samples, probability sampling, and multi-site designs to improve representativeness and generalizability.

Recommendations

Based on the finding that spiritual well-being was positively associated with work attitude, brief and inclusive wellness activities may be incorporated into existing staff development programs, in-service training, or staff meetings. These may include quiet reflection, mindfulness, personal prayer, gratitude reflection, peer mentoring, and meaning-centered discussions on patient care. Such activities should remain voluntary, respectful of diverse beliefs, and designed not to disrupt clinical duties. Nursing administrators may strengthen workplace support by providing access to counseling services, peer support activities, employee assistance programs, and optional spiritual or pastoral care. Nursing education institutions may also integrate spirituality, professional values, compassion, and holistic well-being into classroom and clinical learning through reflective discussions and case-based activities. Future studies may use larger samples, probability sampling, and multi-site designs, and may examine related variables such as burnout, job satisfaction, compassion fatigue, organizational support, work-life balance, and resilience. A proposed output of the study is a brief spiritual wellness program titled "Nurturing the Spirit: A Spiritual Wellness Program for Nurses," which may support spiritual well-being, resilience, peer support, positive work attitudes, and compassionate patient care.

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